

The influence of wood polymer composite (WPC) specimen composition and dimensions on wave propagation

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Abstract Wave propagation velocity has been used to characterize and classify different types of materials. Proper use of this parameter means, it is necessary to know which variables affect it. This study therefore aims to evaluate the influence of composite type and specimen dimensions on the velocity of ultrasonic and stress wave propagation in compression and injection molded specimens produced with 12 different wood-polymer-composite (WPC) formulations and with high-density polyethylene (HDPE), low-density polyethylene (LDPE) and polypropylene (PP) thermoplastics. For wave propagation velocity analysis, the compression-molded specimens were cut into pieces of four different lengths with a nominal thickness of 10 mm, while the injected ones were produced in two lengths and 4 mm nominal thickness. 22 kHz and 45 kHz transducers were used for the ultrasound wave propagation tests. Specimen size affect wave propagation velocity, showing that in the WPC classification the relationships between cross section dimensions (width and thickness) and length and cross section dimensions are important, as are the relationships between these dimensions and wavelength. The type of WPC polymer affected wave propagation velocity, showing that it is feasible to use this parameter in the classification of different polymers. Composition also affected velocity when a single polymer was used, but the influence of the dimensions hinders more conclusive results regarding wave propagation velocity sensitivity in the differentiation of different compositions.

Introduction

Wood polymer composites or wood plastic composites (WPCs) have existed since the 1950s, but in several countries have recently entered in consumer market. WPCs may be manufactured by extrusion, injection molding and compression molding. Extrusion is the process used to blend polymer and wood, and it may also form the final product in a mold at the extruder outlet. In other cases, the extrusion process is used only in blending, while the final product is formed in a molding process by compression or injection.

“Although early WPC products were mainly extruded for profiled sections, nowadays, many injected parts made of WPC are being introduced for various industries, including electrical casings, packaging, daily living supplies, and civil engineering applications” (Gardner et al. 2015). Compression molding has been researched for many years and has been used extensively in the manufacture of automotive parts with WPCs (Matuana and Stark 2015; Al-Oqla and Sapuan 2014). The parts produced in these processes are generally smaller than extruded profiles, and they are often thin, especially those produced by injection molding.

The polymers commonly used in composites are high density polyethylene (HDPE), low density polyethylene (LDPE), polypropylene (PP), and polyvinyl chloride (PVC). They can be used virgin, recycled or mixed (El-Haggar and Kamel 2011). Of these polymers, PVC is the least used due to its higher density than HDPE, LDPE and PP.

Unlike wood panels (particleboards, MDF or OSB), WPC products may be produced in small plants, and are therefore likely to have very different properties. It is therefore important to study simple and accurate ways of assessing the origin and quality of the products produced with these materials. WPC property characterization now involves the destructive evaluation of specimens. This is based on specific standards or, in some cases, standards developed for plastic materials. In Europe, the UNE-CEN/TS 15534 (AENOR 2014) standard was developed to characterize WPC materials or products.

Several studies have shown that it is possible to estimate the physical and mechanical properties of wood and wood panels by non-destructive methods and more specifically by methods using wave propagation (Mendes et al. 2012; Bobadilla et al. 2011, 2012; Hilbers et al. 2012a,b; Silva and Gonçalves 2007; Silva et al. 2008; Gonçalves and Silva 2002, 2003; Tucker et al. 1998). Other materials, such as cement based composites (Garbacz and Garboczi 2003; Sogbey et al. 2014; Garcez et al. 2013) or polymers (Finocchio et al. 2010), have also been considered as candidates for characterization by these non-destructive methods. Ross (2015)

classified methods that use ultrasonic and stress wave propagation velocity in a single group called "longitudinal stress wave techniques".

Some factors may interfere with wave propagation in solid media. Of these, the most important for this study are those that affect flat waves propagating in infinite media, the theoretical hypothesis of wave propagation tests. For a flat wave to propagate in infinite media the dimensions of the medium must be larger than the wavelength (λ).

Considering that frequency is related to wavelength (Equation 1), the choice of this parameter should always be linked to the dimensions of the piece to be tested, so that wave propagation occurs under infinite media.

$$\lambda = \frac{v}{f} \quad (1)$$

Where λ = wavelength; v = wave velocity propagating freely; f = transducer frequency.

According to Bucur (2006), the velocity of wave propagation is strongly and continuously affected by the ratio between the width (b) and thickness (h) of specimen cross-section, as well as the relationship between the path length and cross-section dimensions of the test piece. This is particularly important for the board and plate geometries of the product studied here. In tests on wood at frequencies above 100 kHz, the same author shows that velocity was affected by the frequency, increasing up to 500 kHz and remaining almost constant for higher frequencies. When discussing these results, Bucur (2006) indicates that up to 1 MHz, velocity variation is associated with geometric questions related to wavelength, while above 1 MHz this variation is a result of the combination of material structural dimensions and wavelength.

Considering the above-mentioned aspects, it is important to know the influence of frequency and test piece dimensions on wave propagation velocity, since this can affect the use of this technology in material characterization and classification. This question has therefore been studied by several authors in wood and wood-based materials (Trinca and Gonçalves, 2009; Bartholomeu et al. 2003; Morales et al. 2007; Najafiet al. 2008; Bekhtaet al. 2000), and in plastics (Mazeika et al. 2010).

This study evaluates a non-invasive method using wave propagation (ultrasound and stress wave) to verify its sensitivity in identifying different types of wood polymer composites in small injection or compression molded pieces. As ideally it is desirable to have no boundary condition interference in wave propagation parameters, the interference arising due to small specimen sizes was also investigated.

Material and methods

Materials

Coconut shell flour (*Cocos nucifera* L.) and two different particle sizes pine wood flour (*Pinus taeda* L.) were used. The thick grain wood flour was obtained from forest industry waste, while the thin grain wood flour and the thin grain coconut shell flour were provided by a company that produces this material.

Three kinds of polymers were used in matrix phase composites: high density polyethylene (HDPE), virgin and recycled in a 50/50 mix, low-density polyethylene, (LDPE) and polypropylene (PP). Their properties are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Properties of the polymers used

Property	Standard	LDPE	HDPE	PP
Density (kg m ⁻³)	ASTM D 1505	918	954	900
Fluidity index 190°C / 2.16 kg	ASTM D 1238	8.3	4.5	20
VICAT softening temperature (°C)	ASTM D 1525	86	124	130-160

Yield strength (MPa)	ASTM D 638	9	27	28
Modulus of elasticity - Bendingstrength (MPa)	ASTM D 790	200	1150	1100

Source: BRASKEM (2016)

Experimental Design

In order to evaluate the acoustic properties of the different materials, the composites were produced by varying polymer type, the type of flour and its particle size. The composites were made in the laboratory by extrusion using a co-rotating twin-screw MH-COR-20-32 extruder with 20 mm diameter screws and a length (L) to diameter (D) ratio of 32 with degassing. Like the composites, the polymers were also used unmixed with cellulose, with a total of 15 types of materials in the experimental design (Table 2).

In addition to the matrix (polymers), the process variables were type and proportion of cellulose flour for HDPE and PP, and particle size and type of flour for LDPE. This sample design considered the characteristics of each matrix, since LDPE was the most suitable matrix for thick particles because of its lower density and melting point.

Table 2 Types of composites

Composite	Polymer ¹	Flour ratio ² (%)	Flour type ³
1	HDPE	0	-----
2	HDPE	20	<i>Pinus taeda</i> thin
3	HDPE	40	<i>Pinus taeda</i> thin
4	HDPE	10 + 10	<i>Pinus taeda</i> thin + Coconut Shell
5	HDPE	20 + 20	<i>Pinus taeda</i> thin + Coconut Shell
6	PP	0	-----
7	PP	20	<i>Pinus taeda</i> thin
8	PP	40	<i>Pinus taeda</i> thin
9	PP	10 + 10	<i>Pinus taeda</i> thin + Coconut Shell
10	PP	20 + 20	<i>Pinus taeda</i> thin + Coconut Shell
11	LDPE	0	-----
12	LDPE	40	<i>Pinus taeda</i> thin
13	LDPE	20 + 20	<i>Pinus taeda</i> thin + Coconut Shell
14	LDPE	40	<i>Pinus taeda</i> thick
15	LDPE	20 + 20	<i>Pinus taeda</i> thick + Coconut Shell

¹LDPE = 50% virgin low-density polyethylene + 50% recycled low-density polyethylene; ²Based on weight; ³Average particle diameters of 0.0143; 0.0196 and 0.2599 mm for coconut shell, thin pine and thick pine, respectively

The 15 types of extrusion composites were granulated to obtain compression and injection molded specimens. The compressed specimens were made in a 250 x 300 x 10 mm³ male and female snap-type steel mold with guide pins. After the distribution of granulated composite in the mold, the specimens were subjected to 7.85 MPa pressure and 180° C temperature. After pressing, the mold was cooled in water and the plate was removed manually. 50 x 220 mm² specimens were cut from the plates for the wave propagation tests. After the wave propagation tests on the initial length (220 mm), the specimens were cut into lengths (Table 3 – Groups A to D) and new measurements of wave propagation were conducted. The injection molded specimens were made in a LH injection Himaco 150-80 device, at temperatures varying from 185° C to 200° C, depending on the injected mixture. 80 x 10 x 4 mm³ and 160 x 20 x 4 mm³ specimens were made (Table 3 – Groups E and F).

Table 3 Dimensions of the compression molded pieces (A to D) and injected pieces (E and F) subjected to the tests for ultrasound and stress wave propagation

Group	Length (mm)	Thickness (h) (mm)	Width (b) (mm)	b/h	L/b
A	220	10	50	5.0	4.4
B	120	10	50	5.0	2.4

C	85	10	50	5.0	1.7
D	50	10	85	8.5	0.6
E	160	4	20	5.0	8.0
F	80	4	10	2.5	8.0

Density determination

To obtain the density, the mass was obtained in an analytical balance with a precision of 0.01 g. The stereometrics method was used to determine the volume of 10 mm thick compressed specimens, with the length and width measurements by the analog caliper and thickness measurements using a digital horizontal test indicator. To determine the volume of 4 mm thick injected specimens, the hydrostatic balance method was used, where specimens were immersed in a container with distilled water at 20° C, placed on the analytical balance accurate to 0.01 g. The mass obtained corresponded to the displaced volume of water and it was then recorded as the volume of the specimen.

Wave propagation tests

For the ultrasound wave propagation tests two transducer frequencies were used: 22 kHz, using Sylvatest Duo equipment (CBS-CBT, Lausanne, Switzerland), and 45 kHz using US Lab equipment (Agricef, Campinas, Brazil).

During the test the transducers were positioned at opposite ends of the specimens (direct test) to read the compression wave propagation time (t), which together with the path length (L), in this case specimen length, gave the wave propagation velocity (Equation 2). Electric pulses are produced automatically by the ultrasound equipment. This pulse is transformed into a mechanical pulse by the transmitting transducer. It then passes through the material to the receiving transducer at the other end. This transforms it into an electric pulse that is detected by the equipment to give the propagation time.

$$V = \frac{L}{t} \quad (2)$$

Where V = velocity; L = distance between the transducers or sensors; t = time

In the stress wave device (Fakopp Microsecond Timer, Sopron, Hungary), the pulse was generated by hammer impact on the emission sensor and, after traversing the material, it was received by a signal reception sensor and, in the same way in the ultrasound equipment, gave the wave propagation time. In this type of test the pulse is lower frequency than is the case with ultrasound, generally lower than 20 kHz (Dackermann et al. 2014).

For the ultrasonic and stress wave tests the specimens were on wooden supports and held by a horizontal clamp (Figure 1).

Fig. 1 Representative picture of ultrasound and stress wave tests and schematic drawing of wave velocity measurement

a = Fakopp microsecond timer (Stress wave); b = Emission and reception sensor; c = Horizontal type clamp for fixing specimen; d = Specimen; e = Wooden support; f = Hammer for knock; g = USLab equipment (Ultrasound); h = Transducer; v = velocity; f = frequency; λ = wave length

To include density in the analysis the stiffness coefficient (C) was also calculated by means of Equation 3. This inclusion avoids density interference in the main analyses, consisting of the influence of the composition and dimensions of wood polymer composite (WPC) specimen wave propagation

$$C = \rho V^2 \quad (3)$$

Where ρ = apparent density; V = velocity

Scanning electron microscopy

To visualize the structure of the lower density pieces and compare them with the higher density ones, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was carried out using a VEGA 3 Tescan electronic microscope, with magnifications from 30 to 500 times and 10 KV incident beam energy. The specimens were flexure fractured to observe the internal composition of the composite and, for this purpose the fractured surface was covered with a gold conducting layer of approximately 10 nm. To obtain the microphotographs, the samples were placed on individual 1 cm diameter circular aluminum supports.

Statistical analysis

For each one of the 15 types of extruded composites (Table 2), five compression molded pieces of each of the four dimensions were tested, together with six injected pieces of each of the two dimensions (Table 3), totaling 480 pieces.

To analyze data normality, it was checked whether the skewness and kurtosis values were within the range from -2.0 to +2.0, as well as the linearity of the normal probability plot. After normality was verified parametric statistics and multiple comparison tests were performed.

Results and discussion

Wavelength varies with velocity and frequency (Equation 1). Since the velocity at each frequency varied with the variation of specimen length, the velocity used to calculate the approximate value of wavelength (Table 4) was the maximum velocity obtained in the tests for each treatment and for each transducer frequency in both compression and injection molding. The maximum velocity was adopted because it is considered to correspond closest to the propagation of plane waves in an infinite medium (Bucur 2006).

The wavelength was calculated for each composite (Table 4) to exclude the effect of composition on velocity variation. For the stress waves, as frequency was not determined during the test, wavelength was not calculated. Although the stress wave frequency was not calculated, it is expected that the cross-sectional dimension (b) was not higher than the wavelength for any of the composites, since the frequency is lower than the ultrasonic frequency (Dackermann et al. 2014) and thus the wavelengths will be even higher.

Table 4 Average density for each composite and wavelength (mm) calculated with the maximum ultrasound wave propagation velocities (m/s) in the different test piece lengths and with the frequencies of the ultrasonic transducers (22 kHz and 45 kHz)

Composite	Polymer (matrix)	Density (kg m ⁻³)			Wavelength - λ (mm)			
		Compression means A, B, C, D	Injection groups 160 mm	Injection group E 80 mm	$f=22$ kHz Compression	$f=45$ kHz Compression	$f=22$ kHz Injection	$f=45$ kHz Injection
6	PP	840	950	950	140.3	74.0	127.7	72.7
7	PP	930	970	960	128.3	72.9	111.5	63.3
8	PP	980	1001	990	125.5	73.1	119.0	67.2
9	PP	930	970	960	90.5	54.0	105.3	58.4
10	PP	970	1001	1000	114.8	63.8	80.1	45.0
1	HDPE	890	910	910	111.4	59.5	96.8	55.7
2	HDPE	870	1001	990	94.6	52.5	108.7	63.4
3	HDPE	710	1005	1005	104.3	58.4	87.0	49.2
4	HDPE	930	1001	1000	113.4	63.9	90.6	50.2
5	HDPE	990	1005	830	125.3	69.0	119.0	67.8
11	LDPE	880	930	920	62.6	36.7	52.4	28.9
12	LDPE	790	970	1001	70.5	43.4	80.2	45.1
13	LDPE	880	1000	990	77.1	44.6	73.4	40.8
14	LDPE	820	1000	1000	68.5	42.6	80.3	45.7
15	LDPE	840	950	1000	70.9	42.5	75.1	41.9

* f = frequency of the ultrasound transducer; HDPE: high density polyethylene; LDPE: low density polyethylene; PP: polypropylene

The maximum velocity is expected for a b (width) / h (thickness) ratio from 1 to 2, when both (b and h) are larger than the wavelength. In this condition wave propagation is closer to a plane wave, and less effect of the geometry is expected. If the b/h ratio increases and one or both dimensions become smaller than the wavelength, the velocity obtained in the test will be affected and will have a lower value (Bucur 2006). In this research the b/h ratios were always higher than 2.0 (Table 3).

At 22 kHz transducer frequency, the Group D LDPE polymer specimen has cross-section dimensions (b = 85 mm) greater than the wavelength (Table 4). At 45 kHz transducer frequency all of the Group D composites have specimen cross-section dimensions larger than the

wavelength ($b > \lambda$). For the LDPE polymer, the condition $b > \lambda$ is also applied to specimens in groups A, B and C. The velocities obtained at 45 kHz frequency were higher than those obtained at the 22 kHz frequency and both were higher than those obtained with stress wave (Figure 2), confirming the theoretical statements cited above.

Fig. 2 Behavior of velocity ($V = \text{m s}^{-1}$) and stiffness coefficient ($C = \text{MPa}$) as a function of the length of specimens with the same width and thickness ratio ($b/h = 5$)

V22= ultrasound velocity at 22-kHz frequency; V45= ultrasound velocity at 45-kHz frequency; VSW= stress wave velocity; C22= stiffness coefficient with 22-kHz frequency; C45= stiffness coefficient with 45-kHz frequency; CSW= stiffness coefficient with stress wave; Equal letters indicate statistical equivalences, both for upper and lowercase

For the ratio b/h equal 1, velocity increases with increasing ratio of the length (L) to the specimen cross-section dimensions (L/b) to values close to 20 and, from there, it remains practically constant. Without the interference of the cross section ($b/h \cong 1$ and both larger than λ), velocity increases with increasing specimen length, assuming, in this case, the condition of plane waves in an infinite medium (Bucur 2006). For lumber, research results have shown that the velocity increases with increasing L/λ ratio, becoming approximately constant at ratios higher than 2.0~3.0 (Trinca and Gonçalves 2009; Bucur 2006; Oliveira et al. 2006; Bartholomeu et al. 2003).

In the case of research using plate geometry (Najafiet al. 2008; Mazeika et al. 2010) as test specimens ($h \ll b$ and $L/b < 20$), it is expected from the theoretical bases that the velocities obtained in the tests are influenced by specimen geometry, so it is not appropriate to evaluate the influence of specimen length independently of cross-section.

Composites differed in density at 710 kg m^{-3} – 990 kg m^{-3} for compression molding and 830 kg m^{-3} – 1005 kg m^{-3} for injection molding. This is because of void formation in different stages during both molding processes. According to Smith (2009) defects can be produced inadvertently in composite materials during the manufacturing process. The most important manufacturing defect likely to occur in practice is porosity due to the presence of voids. On the other hand, other microstructural differences between these two different types of molding are not expected, because both are thermoplastic process, which only shape specimens under heat and pressure.

Internal voids are not expected to influence wave propagation, as the wave length associated with the frequencies used (Table 4) is much longer than the size of the voids, which reach a maximum diameter of around 150 μm in injected HDPE composite number 5, group F, and 2.5 mm in compression HDPE composite number 3. For comparison and visualization of the voids, Figure 3 shows micrographs of the sample fracture surfaces of the injected specimens from composite 5, groups E and F, and the compressed specimens of composites number 3 and 5. Injected composite 5 group F dimension samples and compressed composite 3 had the most voids, while injected composite 5 group E dimension samples and compressed composite 5 ones had no voids.

Fig.3 Micrographs of sample fracture surfaces of injected and compressed specimens
a) composite number 5 – dimension group F – injected; b) composite number 5 – dimension group E – injected; c) composite number 3 – dimension groups A,B,C,D – pressed; d) composite number 5 – dimension groups A,B,C,D – pressed

The interaction between ultrasound wave and discontinuities depends on the relative size and orientation of the latter to the wavelength. A discontinuity will result in a local change in acoustic impedance compared to the surrounding material, if its dimensions are large compared with the wavelength (Smith 2009).

Similarly, when studying wave propagation (200 kHz frequency) in porous panels, Sun and Arima (1999) showed that density, internal bond and chip geometry were the main factors influencing wave velocity in particleboard if density is less than about 750 kgm^{-3} . Greater densities show no significant changes in velocity.

Differences in density could arise from variability related with the molding process, interfering with the core objective of analyzing the influence of composite type and specimen dimensions on ultrasound and stress wave propagation. So, for discussions about the influence of composites and cross-section on wave propagation, the stiffness coefficient (C) was added to velocity as an evaluation parameter.

Figure 2 shows that, for ultrasonic waves, maintaining the ratio between specimen width (b) and thickness (h) (groups A, B, C and E of Table 3), there were no statistical differences in velocity and stiffness coefficient on the different specimen lengths (L), even with variation in the L/b ratio (Table 3). For stress waves, there was variation in velocity and stiffness among groups with the same b/h ratio, probably because specimen cross-section dimension is inferior to the wavelength. For the same L/b ratio (groups E and F) but with different b/h ratio, the statistical comparison test using the confidence interval of the difference between means showed that, for both ultrasound and stress waves, the velocity and stiffness coefficients are different, with 95% confidence.

The variation observed for wood (Bucur 2006, Trinca and Gonçalves 2009, Bartholomeu et al. 2003) of increased velocity with reduction of the b/h ratio maximum value with b/h near 1 was observed for wood polymer composite using ultrasound but not stress waves. There was a small increase in velocity for $b/h = 8$ that was more evident in the stiffness coefficient (Figure 4). This result for stress wave may be associated with the relationship between wavelength and cross-section dimensions, making stress wave propagation behavior more like surface waves ("love" waves) than compression waves (Bucur 2006, Bartholomeu et al. 2003).

Fig.4 Behavior of velocity and stiffness coefficient as a function of the width and thickness ratio

The results of wave velocity for the different compositions/polymers indifferent specimen dimensions vary from approximately 1000 to 3000 m s⁻¹ for ultrasound and from 800 to 2000 m s⁻¹ for stress wave. These velocity ranges are similar to those obtained by other researchers who used similar composites (Najafi et al. 2008; Mazeika et al. 2010).

Najafi et al. (2008) obtained mean values of ultrasonic wave velocity varying from 2285 to 2784 m s⁻¹ for tests performed with 16 kHz frequency transducers in polypropylene and coniferous wood composites, with wood proportions varying from 50% to 70% and with fiberglass proportions varying from 0% to 15%. In the case of the research by Najafi et al. (2008), the dimensions of the cross section ($b = 70$ mm and $h = 10$ mm) were both less than the wavelength (about 180 mm) and therefore, as in this study, the volume wave condition was not obtained.

Mazeika et al. (2010) carried out ultrasonic tests on HDPE tubes using higher frequencies (1 MHz, 3 MHz and 5 MHz) than those used in this research (22 kHz and 45 kHz). The tests were performed on constant section plates (50 mm x 50 mm) by varying the thickness (2.55 mm, 5.07 mm, 7.5 mm, 10.07 mm, 12.5 mm, 15.07 mm and 17.69 mm), with the propagation waves analyzed in the thickness of the plates. Due to the high frequencies, the cross section and path length (thickness) were always larger than the wavelengths (about 2 mm for the 1 MHz frequency, 0.67 mm for the 3 MHz frequency and 0.40 mm for the 5 MHz frequency). The values presented by the authors showed variations of about 1% in velocity between plates of the same thickness, which corresponds to the error expected for ultrasound tests. This shows that there was no variation in velocity with path length, which is an expected result for the propagation of volume waves in an infinite medium. Considering the average values obtained in the different thicknesses, velocity variation with frequency was also small (about 1%), ranging from 2230 m/s at 1 MHz to 2255 m/s at 5 MHz. The variation of signal attenuation with frequency was significant, increasing from 0.31 dB/mm at 1 MHz frequency to 1.5 dB / mm at 5 MHz.

Bekhta et al. (2000) working with wood panels (particleboards, OSB and MDF), obtained a clear reduction in velocity with increasing b/h ratio, as expected theoretically. These authors

used specimen dimensions of b (20 mm, 40 mm, 60 mm, 80 mm, 100 mm, 150 mm and 200 mm) and h (16 mm) higher than the wavelength. This condition was obtained because they used a 200 kHz frequency ($\lambda \cong 15$ mm), characterizing plane waves. For a 50 kHz frequency ($\lambda \cong 60$ mm) and 100 kHz frequency ($\lambda \cong 30$ mm) this tendency was not so clear, since the wave is affected by the specimen dimensions and wavelength ratio, as also occurred in this paper, mainly for stress wave (Figure 4). Velocity increased by about 30% with frequency increased from 50 kHz to 200 kHz (Bekhta et al. 2000). This result also shows that velocity is affected by specimen geometry. The current results also show differences of around 30% between velocities obtained using 45-kHz and 22-kHz transducers.

Statistical analysis in Table 5 shows that, despite the effect of specimen dimension on the velocity of wave propagation, polymer type affected velocity and the stiffness coefficient in the same way for all dimensions. This was so for ultrasonic waves and for stress waves. This result shows that the effect of polymer variation on velocity and stiffness coefficient was superior to the interference caused by dimensions. This makes it possible to classify the different polymers analyzed, independently of the specimen dimensions used in the tests.

Table 5 Mean wave velocities (first line $m\ s^{-1}$) and stiffness coefficient (second line MPa) results of the multiple comparison test in the different polymers, considering the variation in specimen dimensions (width x thickness x length)

Dimension (mm)	50 x 10 x 220 Compression	20 x 4 x 160 Injection	50 x 10 x 120 Compression	50 x 10 x 85 Compression	10 x 4 x 80 Injection	85 x 10 x 50 Compression
Ultrasound 22 kHz						
PP	2244 a 4468 A	2189 a 4533 A	2348 a 4774 A	2385 a 4717 A	2401 a 5439 A	2609 a 5826 A
HDPE	1875 b 3495 B	1974 b 4227 B	1968 b 3845 B	1984 b 4091 B	2103 b 4595 B	2162 b 4745 B
LDPE	1401 c 1655 C	1439 c 2074 C	1405 c 1648 C	1397 c 1657 C	1562 c 2472 C	1486 c 1879 C
Ultrasound 45 kHz						
PP	2588 a 5928 A	2513 a 5972 A	2655 a 6143 A	2680 a 6136 A	2794 a 7298 A	3025 a 7963 A
HDPE	2174 b 4725 B	2258 b 5548 B	2224 b 4866 B	2284 b 5184 B	2456 b 6360 B	2514 b 6246 B
LDPE	1576 c 2094 C	1647 c 2723 C	1585 c 2099 C	1646 c 2300 C	1797 c 3281 C	1822 c 2828 C
Stress waves						
PP	1841 a 2933 A	1887 a 3401 A	1683 a 2420 A	1550 a 2038 A	1716 a 2802 A	1332 a 1512 A
HDPE	1521 b 2389 B	1746 b 3253 B	1438 b 2081 B	1249 b 1602 B	1509 b 2308 B	1085 b 1196 B
LDPE	1168 c 1651 C	1298 c 1686 C	1076 c 1347 C	1083 c 1100 C	1206 c 1470 C	1004 c 1156 C

* Equal letters, with reference to each column, indicate statistically equivalent values (lowercase for wave velocity and uppercase for stiffness coefficient)

Considering the proportion and flour type used in the composites for each polymer, statistical analysis (Table 6) shows that, regardless of the variation in specimen dimensions, for PP and LDPE the pure polymer specimens were statistically different from composites specimens, with the lowest wave velocity and stiffness coefficients. For PP polymer it was also possible to statistically differentiate the composition with 40% *Pinus taeda* L. as the one with the highest wave velocity and stiffness coefficients, regardless of specimen dimensions. In the other cases, the influence of composition on wave velocity or stiffness coefficient variation was dependent on specimen dimension, so it was not possible to reach conclusions about the influence of composition on these variables.

Table 6 Mean wave velocities (first line m s⁻¹) and stiffness coefficient (second line MPa) using 22 kHz (US22) and 45 kHz (US45) transducers, and stress wave (SW) in specimen produced with the different types of composites (Cp) for each polymer and specimen made by different process and with different dimensions (width x thickness x length)

Dimensions (mm)	50 x 10 x 220 compression			20 x 4 x 160 injection			50 x 10 x 120 compression			50 x 10 x 85 compression			10 x 4 x 80 injection			85 x 10 x 50 compression			
Cp	Polymer (matrix)	US22	US45	SW	US22	US45	SW	US22	US45	SW	US22	US45	SW	US22	US45	SW	US22	US45	SW
6	PP	2029a	2305a	1654a	1604a	1817a	1382a	2182a	2458a	1514a	2113a	2409a	1338a	1720a	1987a	1305a	2287a	2682a	1190a
		3660A	4727A	2435A	2489A	3217A	1867A	4021A	5107A	1938A	3883A	4939A	1525A	2887A	3811A	1617A	4480A	6122A	1205A
7	PP	2243b	2605b	1843b	2318c	2664c	2000c	2332c	2613b	1705bc	2479bc	2719b	1591bc	2551c	3013c	1798c	2588b	2937b	1337b
		4885B	6583B	3290B	5309C	7008C	3957C	5098C	6396C	2728B	5864B	7046B	2411B	6416C	8898C	3175B	6412B	8245B	1703B
8	PP	2449c	2830c	1985c	2487e	2889d	2107d	2546d	2859c	1808c	2565c	2887c	1661d	2744d	3165d	1885e	2873c	3219c	1435c
		6010C	8024C	3949C	6341E	8601E	4517E	6503B	8206B	3282C	6616C	8383C	2775C	7561D	10017D	3593C	8317C	10430C	2072C
9	PP	2226b	2596b	1868b	2191b	2519b	1923b	2286bc	2644b	1667b	2348b	2657b	1569b	2439b	2815b	1746b	2600b	3055bc	1335b
		4717B	6415B	3314B	4776B	6274B	3640B	4988B	6648B	2648B	5208B	6671B	2328B	5808B	7731B	2974B	6405B	8847B	1681B
10	PP	2272b	2605b	1856b	2344d	2675c	2024c	2395c	2698b	1718bc	2397b	2725b	1592c	2550c	2987c	1844d	2696bc	3234c	1365bc
		5224B	6865B	3485B	5646D	7353D	4216D	5660B	7187B	2914BC	5597B	7228B	2469B	6669C	9224C	3511C	7074B	10176C	1817B
1	HDPE	1799a	2070a	1344a	2031d	2320d	1807d	1843a	2113a	1289a	1769a	2154a	1218b	2263c	2613c	1666d	1980a	2396bc	1034b
		3150B	4167B	1760AB	3809B	4998C	3039B	3138B	4133B	1542A	2752A	4069AB	1299B	4698C	6320C	2575C	3438A	5036B	938B
2	HDPE	1865a	2155ab	1562c	1918b	2180b	1691b	1949c	2221b	1452b	1964bc	2221a	1184ab	2101b	2482b	1432b	2208b	2491b	1067b
		3176B	4238B	2234B	3769B	4859B	2933B	3443BC	4478BC	1921B	3397A	4333B	1224B	4488C	6232C	2052B	4320B	5495BC	998B
3	HDPE	1812a	2062a	1471bc	2169e	2505e	1856e	1901b	2111a	1421b	1949b	2210a	1150a	2312d	2770d	1626c	1986a	2292a	984a
		2374A	3073A	1562A	5026D	6718E	3673D	2666A	3287A	1493A	2749A	3521A	950A	5634D	8099D	2846D	2835A	3777A	696A
4	HDPE	1858a	2201b	1490c	1787a	2042a	1609a	1994c	2277b	1452b	2083cd	2372b	1315c	1911a	2208a	1392a	2220b	2593d	1122c
		3229B	4534B	2075AB	3273A	4282A	2670A	3766C	4910C	1997B	4120B	5344C	1641C	3714B	4956B	1950B	4669B	6376C	1194C
5	HDPE	2043b	2384c	1736d	1968c	2245c	1766c	2154d	2397c	1574c	2153d	2464b	1378d	1928a	2206a	1428b	2417c	2796e	1217d
		4163C	5675C	3025C	4167C	5398D	3382C	4623D	5722D	2467C	4716B	6171D	1937D	3118A	4097A	1715A	5946C	7938D	1506D
11	LDPE	1237a	1396a	1006a	1019a	1147a	932a	1253a	1409a	952a	1265a	1506a	995a	1147a	1290a	902a	1313a	1580a	897a
		1411A	1798A	934A	979A	1245A	821A	1379A	1743A	795A	1421A	2014A	878A	1240A	1561A	761A	1534A	2221A	713A
12	LDPE	1436c	1619c	1193b	1616d	1857c	1432c	1440cd	1605b	1098bc	1401b	1684c	1087b	1733d	2013d	1393d	1513b	1881b	1046c
		1674B	2125B	1155B	2596C	3418C	2034D	1685B	2091B	977B	1579B	2278B	950AB	3080D	4182D	1805D	1837B	2842B	878B
13	LDPE	1480d	1656d	1230c	1458b	1688b	1336b	1459d	1649c	1112cd	1488c	1754d	1168c	1587b	1819b	1229b	1605c	1971c	1046c
		1943D	2433D	1343C	2167B	2897B	1832C	1852C	2367C	1076C	2013C	2793C	1239C	2549B	3344B	1529B	2341D	3525C	993C
14	LDPE	1458cd	1636cd	1226c	1614d	1840c	1451d	1467d	1678c	1136d	1435b	1668c	1097b	1732d	2006d	1323d	1472b	1814b	1012b
		1796C	2259C	1270C	2654C	3441C	2152E	1801BC	2356C	1079C	1730B	2337B	1012B	3047D	4078D	1774D	1822B	2770B	861B
15	LDPE	1394b	1575b	1184b	1485c	1703b	1340b	1404b	1583b	1084b	1394b	1619b	1069b	1613c	1857c	1254c	1526b	1866b	1023b
		1617B	2064B	1168B	2139B	2813B	1745B	1679B	2136B	1002BC	1702B	2297B	1002B	2690C	3524C	1600C	2042C	3055B	914B

*The same letters (lowercase for wave velocity and uppercase for stiffness coefficient), with reference to each column, indicate statistically equivalent values; Velocity and stiffness coefficient values increase in alphabetical order; HDPE: high-density polyethylene; LDPE: low-density polyethylene; PP: polypropylene

Conclusion

In this paper, a non-invasive wave propagation (ultrasound and stress wave) method was investigated to verify its sensitivity in identifying different types of wood polymer composites. As ideally it is desirable to have no interference by boundary conditions in wave propagation parameters, the interference arising from specimen dimensions was also investigated.

If the wavelength is no greater than both dimensions of specimen cross-section, velocity is influenced by frequency and decreases with falling frequency.

If the wavelength is greater than at least one dimension of the specimen cross-section, there is no variation in the velocity of wave propagation in different specimen lengths for the same ratio between specimen width and thickness. Velocity increases with reduction of the width/thickness ratio to values near 1.0.

Despite the effect of specimen dimensions on wave propagation velocity, polymer type affected velocity in the same way for all dimensions for ultrasonic and stress waves. This result shows that polymer type significantly affects velocity, overcoming variations due to specimen dimensions.

The influence of specimen dimensions means that there is insufficient sensitivity for wave propagation to distinguish different proportions and flour types (compositions) for a specific polymer. Nevertheless, in two of them (PP and LDPE) it was possible to distinguish the composition with the lowest velocity (zero flour addition) from the highest.

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